

Preparation of *o*-Hydroxy-ketoanils

G. B. JOSHI, G. S. PATEL* and V. M. THAKOR.**

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar

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o-Hydroxy-ketoanils have been prepared by condensing 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone with aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline and α -naphthylamine using anhydrous zinc chloride as a condensing agent. Their absorption spectra in ultra-violet, visible and infra red-regions were taken. They are found to be chelating agents for copper (II), nickel(II) and cobalt (II).

THE anils have been prepared by different workers,¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our work on preparation of *o*-Hydroxy-ketoanils⁵, we have condensed 2-Hydroxy - 5- methyl - acetophenone with aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline and α -naphthylamine, using zinc chloride as condensing agent. The anils have been characterised as benzoyl derivative prepared by Schotten-Baumann reaction⁶.

The absorption spectra of anils in ultra-violet and visible region shows three absorption maxima as recorded in Table 1. The values suggest that the para substitution to benzene nucleus attached to nitrogen has no appreciable effect on the position of absorption maxima but when the naphthyl group is attached to nitrogen, a dampening of the absorption maxima is observed. This may be due to the bulkiness of the group. The anils are yellow in colour, giving yellow solution in alcohol and other organic solvents but they do not show any characterstic absorption maxima in the blue region.

The trailing portion of the absorption spectra which extends into the blue region of the spectrum causes yellow or yellowish orange colour.

The infrared spectra of these anils were recorded. They show $-C=N-$ absorption band between 1625-1620 Cm^{-1} and substitution at para position to the benzene nucleus attached to nitrogen atom or at carbonyl-carbon has no effect on the position of $-C=N-$ band. Fabian, Legrand and Poirier⁶ had shown that the $-C=N-$ absorption in the open chain systems occurs within the range 1600-1640 Cm^{-1} but the lowering in

value may be due to conjugate chelation in the system. The shifting of the $-C=N-$ absorption bands to lower frequency due to conjugate chelation (Hydrogen bond formation) is similar to the frequency shifts of carbonyl group with an *o*-hydroxy substituent.⁷

These anils are found to be chelating agents for copper (II) nickel (II) and cobalt (II) and are represented by the general structure.

Experimental :

Preparation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenoneanil : 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone was prepared by the Fries reaction of *p*-cresyl acetate.⁸

2-Hydroxy -5-methyl acetophenone (0.1 mole) base (0.1mole) and anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) were mixed and heated on oil bath at 160° for half an hour and then the temperature was raised to 180°. It was kept at this temperature for five minutes and was allowed to cool. The anil was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform was distilled out from the extract and the product was crystallised from eathanol.

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION MAXIMA AND M.P. OF THE ANILS AND M.P. OF THEIR BENZOYL DERIVATIVES.

Sr. No.	Anils.	m.p. of the anil °C	m.p. of the benzoyl derivative	Ist $\lambda_{\text{max. nm}}$ (log ϵ)	IIInd $\lambda_{\text{max. nm}}$ (log ϵ)	IIIrd $\lambda_{\text{max. nm}}$ (log ϵ)
1.	2-Hydroxy-5-methylaceto-phenoneanil.	109°C	149°C	335.0 (4.2424)	260.0 (4.6029)	226.0 (4.9563)
2.	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-aceto-phenone (p) tolyl.	130°C	154°C	335.0 (4.3226)	260.0 (4.6327)	227.0 (4.8422)
3.	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-aceto-phenone (p) anisil.	125°C	155°C	335.0 (3.3955)	259.0 (4.6904)	228.0 (4.3434)
4.	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-aceto-phenone (p) chlorophenylanil.	135°C	184°C	340.0 (3.9246)	259.0 (4.2933)	232.0 (4.5662)
5.	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-aceto-phenone (p) bromophenylanil.	129°C	169°C	335.0 (3.9001)	259.0 (4.2891)	221.0 (4.8688)
6.	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-aceto-phenone (α) naphthil.	126 C	157°C	335.0 (4.0251)	—	—

*Chemistry Department, Bhavans College, Ahmedabad.

**Principal, M. P. Shah Science College, Surendranagar.

Several anils and their benzoyl derivatives which have been prepared are given in Table 1.

All compounds described in Table 1 gave correct carbon hydrogen analysis.

The absorption spectra of the anils in ultra-violet and visible region were taken in ethanol, using Unicchem-spectrophoto meter. The Infra red spectra were taken I.R. 5 using nujol as medium.

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